

Supporting the Natural Disaster Management Distributing Federated Intelligence over the Cloud-Edge Continuum: the TEMA Architecture

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ABSTRACT

Natural disasters are more and more often present in our daily life. Many are the cases where these events affect people and economies. In this context, there is the need for a technological intervention in support of first responders, with solutions capable of make decisions on the disaster areas. Indeed, considering these scenarios are time-sensitive, the intention is moving the computation units closer to those areas. In this paper, we propose a computing continuum architecture for offloading distributed intelligences over cloud, edge and deep edge layers. Exploiting the federated learning paradigm, enables mobile and stationary devices to independently train local models, contributing to the creation of the global common model.

KEYWORDS

Federated Learning, Artificial Intelligence, Computing Continuum, Robot Operating System, Software Architecture

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, we have assisted in the rise of the number of natural disasters all around the world. In this regard, the Institute for Economics and Peace [9] captured data between the 1900 and 2019, revealing an increase from 39 incidents in 1960 to 396 in 2019. The largest amount of natural disasters was experienced in 2005, where 90000 people died after 442 incidents and another 160 million people were in need of immediate assistance. As if that was not enough, natural disasters represent an issue also for the economies of countries. Once again, the Institute for Economics and Peace reported that the resulting cost of addressing damage caused by natural disasters has risen from US\$ 50 billion per year in the 1980s to US\$ 200 billion per year in the last decade. There is, therefore, the need for interventions aimed at preserving the fragility of lands and supporting the first responders as soon as the disaster happens, as well as during the following hours.

Although some software architectures have been proposed for facing the needs that climate change (e.g., flood, wildfire, tornado, tsunami, earthquake) pointed out, only a few are the solutions that involve distributed artificial intelligence and even fewer are the solutions that involve the computing continuum. The Trusted

Extremely Precise Mapping and Prediction for Emergency Management (TEMA) is a Horizon Europe project that aims at i) improving natural disaster management (NDM) using new digital technologies and extreme data analytics, ii) improving and accelerating extreme data analytics, by increasing trustworthiness, accuracy and responsiveness of extreme data analysis algorithms and iii) improving and accelerating emergency phenomenon modeling, evolution predictions, simulation and interactive visualization.

In this paper, we propose a novel software architecture for facing the TEMA issues. The architecture aims at integrating the capacity of the computing continuum paradigm of distributing computation near the data source with the need of running artificial intelligence model in devices deployed in remote and hard accessible areas. Therefore, we propose to exploit the capacity of federated learning for training models on a bunch of clients with a small dataset. All of them will participate in the training of a unique artificial intelligence, which will be distributed back for running predictions.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. The motivation why building a new software architecture for achieving the TEMA needs is described in Section 2. Related works are, indeed, reported in Section 3, while an overview of the architecture is available in Section 4. Conclusion remarks and future research activities are, finally, discussed in Section 5.

2 MOTIVATION

The TEMA architecture was built relying on the end-user requirements, as emerging from the four pilot cases belonging to the project. The Trial Guidance Methodology [8] was followed to collect the requirements, adopting a systematic and collaborative approach to discover the needs of the NDM actors and to facilitate the process. The analysis was done studying the gaps before, during or after a natural disaster, administering surveys asking first responders the technical solutions that they would like to have in their operations and, therefore, writing the storytelling of the end-users. What emerged addressed the motivation to build the TEMA architecture. In particular, the main requirements were:

- the ability to collect and share crucial information: digital transformation can assist first responders and command

control in optimizing critical information, especially the phases of prepare recovery in a natural disaster [1];

- lack of an enhanced sharing information tool: current information sharing systems need to be evaluated for their quality and if they can be understood by the end-users as there are interdependencies that may deter stakeholders from using information sharing optimally [6];
- fusing many heterogeneous extreme data sources: smart drone and in-situ sensors, remote sensing data, topographical data, meteorological data/predictions, and geosocial media data (text, image, and videos);
- advanced and interactive visualization systems, combining data fusion capabilities for enabling critical real-time decision support features.

On the other hand, a natural disaster scenario is typically characterized by energy- and Internet-disconnected areas, where battery-powered devices (e.g., drones, weather stations) are used for supporting first responders (e.g., civil protection, firefighters) during the exploration and rescue missions. At the same time, a coordination center monitors the operations from remote, often facing the issue of transmitting data over a satellite network, which increases the latency and reduces the possibility to make decisions in real-time. TEMA solution meets those requirements, by developing a cloud-edge intelligence platform, as explained in the next sections.

3 BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

The progressive convergence of cloud computing and Internet of Things (IoT) devices is resulting in the computing continuum [3, 11]. The concept of edge computing first became to represent a middle layer, where data and computation were migrated in runtime, and later was fused with the IoT devices, because these increasingly acquired computational capacity. In the context of natural disasters, few are the scientific works available in literature and they come from the same research group. Balouek-Thomert et al. was firstly proposing in 2020 [4] a solution for harnessing the computing continuum for urgent science, that is the time-critical, data-driven scientific workflows that can leverage distributed data sources in a timely way to facilitate important decision-making. An Early Earthquake Warning (EEW) workflow was used as a driver for proposing a system stack that can enable the fluid integration of distributed analytics across a dynamic infrastructure spanning the computing continuum. In 2021 [5], Balouek-Thomert et al. proposed to exploit the edge computing capabilities for stream-based processing. The faced challenges range from addressing the complex and constrained characteristics of resources to a large set of heterogeneous data processing and management frameworks. The authors introduced a hierarchical approach for modeling distributed stream-based applications on computing continuum. Finally, in 2022 [2], Balouek-Thomert et al. discussed research directions for tackling i) fire science scenario that includes sensors at the edge of the network for smoke detection and ii) computational models launched in the cloud for wildfire simulation and air quality assessment.

An important aspect of TEMA is enabling intelligence for supporting the first responders. In this context, the scientific community proposed several works that are summarized in [15]. What the TEMA architecture is interested on is driving the intelligence at

the edge of the network [7]. For this reason, we propose to exploit the computational capacity of federated learning [12]. This is a machine learning technique that trains an algorithm over independent sessions running on clients, each using its own dataset. Federated learning enables multiple nodes to build a common model through a number of training iterations (rounds). Such a technology addresses critical issues, such as data access, data privacy and latency. When applied to natural disasters, federated learning has some solutions. For example, Tehseen et al. in [19, 20] presented a framework for training earthquake predicting models. Local models have been aggregated using the novel FedQuake algorithm to generate a global model on the central server. Supriya et al., instead, proposed in [18] a swarm intelligence-based federated learning aggregation method for early detecting of forest fires.

Not much software architectures were proposed for enabling intelligence as a decision-maker support of first responder in the context of natural disaster. Torresan et al. proposed in 2016 [21] a decision support system for the regional risk assessment of climate change impacts in coastal zones. The architecture is well-defined and tested in a relevant scenario, but this lacks of the cutting-edge technologies that today characterize the design of modern architectures. More recently, Zhang et al. [22] proposed a model driven architecture in GIS-based decision support system for flood management. These solutions do not enable intelligent computation, neither at the edge of the network nor on a computing continuum scenario. In our knowledge, there are no software architectures that are designed at the cross of intelligence and computing continuum. The following Sections describe the TEMA vision about such an architecture and point out the major components needed for achieving the claimed goals.

4 ARCHITECTURE

The following section discusses the components and the architecture designed to distribute intelligence over the cloud-edge continuum, supporting the management of natural disasters. In this regard, we considered the constraints and the gaps highlighted in the Section 2. As a result, we drew the architectures represented in Figures 4 and 3 with a focus, respectively, on data and computation flows.

The architecture represents how the intelligent processing is distributed over the continuum. The continuum scenario in which the operations are carried on is composed by two edge layers and one cloud layer, as shown in Figure 1. From the bottom, the first edge layer is named deep edge. It is composed by autonomous and/or mobile devices (e.g., autonomous unmanned vehicles, base stations). Even if this could be considered an Internet of Things layer, the devices are more powerful (e.g., NVIDIA Jetson Orin) and able to make autonomous computations. The second edge layer is composed by one or more base stations. This is, therefore, the computation area that supports the devices on the field, placed side by side the first responder's mobile stations (e.g., mobile control room). For example, this could be a powerful computer or a small rack. The cloud layer facilitates the remote support (e.g., control room) and provide extreme powerful resource for huge computation requirements. While the cloud to edges communication is fully promoted for the injection of new features or top-down order,

Figure 1: The computational workflow starts from the deep edge and offloads up toward the cloud.

the viceversa should be limited for supporting response times as close as real-time. We turned away from the classical fog notation, because the architecture is mostly focused on the computational point of view, while a fog infrastructure is more related to network capabilities. Computation is provided by a *computation unit*, which is a resource-constrained (e.g., Raspberry Pi, NVIDIA Jetson Nano, NVIDIA Jetson Orin) or a powerful computer able to process tasks, according to the layer where it is deployed. A *task* is the small component executed by the computation units. The computing offloading follows the deep edge-to-edge-to-cloud (and viceversa) rule, avoiding any interaction between the deep edge and the cloud. The rule’s goal is gradually moving the tasks among the computation units, encouraging the use of units i) closest to the field and ii) less expensive from the energy point of view.

4.1 From the deep edge point of view

Starting the description of the architecture from the bottom, the first layer to discuss is the deep edge. From the computation point of view, the deep edge is composed by a *computation unit* built within an agent. The idea of proposing an agent is borrowed from the artificial intelligence field. Indeed, an agent is a component able to interact with the environment where it is deployed to make observations and act by means of actions. The agent is drawn in Figure 2.

The devices are the only components included in the deep edge layer. They are heterogeneous by design and represent mobile (e.g., drones, autonomous vehicles, robots) and stationary (e.g., weather stations) devices involved in the field. The devices are resource-constrained and, typically, battery powered. These are managed by the first responders and perform following a centralized or decentralized approach (e.g., client-server or peer-to-peer model). Moreover, the devices are organized in heterogeneous fleets, where

Figure 2: The agent is the core architecture for making computation on the deep edge.

subgroups of them can be involved in specific tasks by defining a dedicated network overlay.

At the first running, the devices are clean of tasks. The only component installed is the agent represented in Figure 2, which allows the baseline operations (e.g., self-management, networking, resource monitor). The agent’s *Tasks Scheduler* is in charge of reading the configuration file pushed by the fleet administrator. Such file uses a human- and machine-readable markup language, such as JSON or YAML. The file includes the services selected by a maintained list and identifies the processing targets of the device. The *Tasks Scheduler* queries a cloud repository and starts a pulling process to set up the device. Pulled tasks are, therefore, stored in the *Tasks Repository* for future use. As soon as all tasks are pulled in, the *Tasks Scheduler* informs the *Computation Manager* to run the tasks. Therefore, the latter is involved for running tasks as instances of the services. From that moment on, the device performs the selected tasks and operates on the field. The *Computation Manager* provides three modules related with the intelligent capabilities of the proposed architecture. The *Training Module* abstracts the training capabilities, running models developed with the most known framework (e.g., Tensorflow, PyTorch). Given the distributed and decentralized nature of the deep edge scenario, the *Federated Learning Module* provides the capability to distribute the training over a number of clients. As a result, the training may speed up and data privacy may be maintained. Finally, the *Inference Module* allows devices to forecast data according to the trained model. While tasks are running, the *Resource Monitor* monitors the used resources (CPU, memory, inbound/outbound network, energy consumption). Indeed, a resource-constrained device is limited both in computational power and energy. In this regard, tasks could not have enough resources to run or complete the processing. Therefore, the *Computation Manager* executes an offloading algorithm for moving the tasks to the upper edge layer, where the ground station may continue the computation.

Mobile devices (e.g., drones, rovers) are often controlled with the Robot Operating System (ROS). This is a middleware designed to build and reuse software for intrinsically distributed robot architectures. Inside the ROS middleware, a set of processes can be represented by a graph where nodes can send and receive information through topics. ROS version 2 is built upon the Data Distribution Service Layer (DDS) that provides a publish-subscribe pattern for sending and receiving data. Data-producer nodes create topics and publish samples that are received from nodes that declare (subscribe) interest in that topics. The components of the *computational unit* shown in Figure 2 are thought to be ROS packages. They communicate, therefore, using the publish-subscribe mechanism provided by that middleware, which uses the Real-Time Publish Subscribe (RTPS) protocol. RTPS is designed to run on an unreliable transport mechanism, such as UDP/IP. This fits the requirements of the deep edge, where mobile devices take in and out from opportunistic networks. However, the protocols implement reliability in the transfer of issues and state. RTPS takes, moreover, advantage of the multicast capabilities of the transport mechanism, where one message from a sender can reach multiple receivers. Communication with public Internet, as in the case of offloading from a layer to the upper one, is provided via classic HTTP REST APIs.

4.2 From the edge point of view

Moving one layer further up, the deep edge becomes edge. In this layer, the used hardware is a small portable computer or datacenter. This is better known as a ground station, a ground-based computer, that communicates with UAV via wireless telemetry. This displays real-time information of the aerial robots, such as performance and position, controls the flight and uploads services on the fly. Such a device could be as small as a carrying case or big enough to be part of an off-road car, which acts as a mobile control room.

Figure 3: The edge layer represents the computation capabilities of the ground stations.

This layer involves the human intervention for driving the aerial robots (e.g., exploration of a specific area). Indeed, backup pilots observe the flight behavior through the ground station and they are ready to take over the control if the need arises. On the other way, this is the first interface of first responders and emergency teams.

All information gathered on the mission are available through the ground station and used for giving high level commands.

From the computation point of view, the edge layer has the same architecture as the deep edge but a bigger hardware capacity. The *computational unit* is, therefore, deployed with the same components and characteristics. In this regard, what was discussed in the section above is still valid for the edge layer. However, given its nature as a hub for the deep edge devices, this is often used as a server for centralized communication or a central node for decentralized communication. When the intelligent computation is distributed over the federated learning concept, the ground station acts like the server, running aggregation strategies (e.g., FedAvg [12]) and building the global model. The edge layer is also responsible for the first level of offloading. As mentioned in this Section, the offloading is gradually promoted from the lower layer to the upper layer. Deep edge devices with limited resources available may offload the computation to the ground station, which may face multiple tasks at once. Nevertheless, the edge ground station is also battery-powered and may run out of charge. As a result, computation could be offloaded to the upper layer, which is the cloud. Communication between the edge layer and the cloud is anyway not recommended because of the need to maintain a short latency. Network infrastructure could be destroyed by the natural disaster or not available, because the event happens in a remote area (e.g., wild forest, mountains). In that cases, the only available communication is the satellite (e.g., Starlink), which is not quick enough to have (near-)real-time decision-making.

4.3 From the cloud point of view

NDM is a multifaceted challenge that demands the coordination of numerous resources and skills. Cloud technologies can significantly enhance the effectiveness of these management activities and are poised to assume an increasingly pivotal role. TEMA's aspiration is to establish an architecture that prioritizes flexibility, primarily aimed at facilitating interoperability among devices, artificial intelligence tools, and software solutions. This will be achieved by setting forth minimum interoperability requirements and optimizing their integration within a unified cloud and edge data and processing environment. The architecture's overarching objectives are to be both straightforward and adaptable, catering to the diverse needs of stakeholders and serving as a viable solution in various contexts where disparate data sources and field devices are utilized. The application layer encompasses all the high-level services that end-users will utilize in disaster management scenarios. These services will be accessible to field operators and decision-makers who oversee emergency response efforts from operations centers. Dashboards will be designed to aggregate valuable information, allowing for the tracking of emergency situations and significant events' progression. For instance, it would be beneficial to have a single integrated view of a map displaying the real-time development of a fire, highlighting buildings at risk, and projecting the fire's future path. Digital Twins can be generated to represent specific geographical areas and integrate data from various sources, such as sensors, satellites, and mobile devices. This data can be leveraged to continuously monitor environmental conditions and identify early warning signs for potential natural disasters like

Figure 4: The cloud layer represents the computation and storing capabilities of a powerful datacenter.

earthquakes, floods, wildfires, and storms. The processing layer is established through a toolbox designed to support the end-user services within the TEMA architecture. The data analysis toolbox encompasses both generic big data tools and specialized analytical tools tailored for disaster management, primarily relying on artificial intelligence models. This toolbox must offer the capability to process data in both batch and near-real-time modes. Furthermore, the toolbox should enable the distributed deployment of various segments of the data analytics tools across different levels of the architecture, including the edge and cloud or on-premises environments. This approach ensures efficient utilization of available storage and processing capacity. To be integrated into the Toolbox, a software component must adhere to a set of requirements. Regardless of the programming language or technology used, it must have an accessible and open API interface and be deployable within a container, such as a Docker container. At the cloud side, the integration layer oversees collecting and unifying data from the various sources storing data resulting from the processing performed by the TEMA tools, providing a publish/subscribe mechanism for the

purpose of triggering different tools in a processing chain. In order to guarantee data integration and interoperability, the core of the cloud layer relies on the Digital Enabler (DE), a data driven, native cloud ecosystem platform powered by Engineering Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A. [16], based on Open Standards and Open APIs.

Digital Enabler enables data discovery, data collection, data harmonization and data visualization [10]. The DE will be the bridge among the layers. The data will come, mainly, from the edge layer, collecting information in the field, and will be made available to the Toolbox components through the DE FIWARE Context Broker [14] and DE Object Storage [13] (two of the main components of the Digital Enabler) to be processed and visualized.

The Object Storage will be responsible to store the data and the Context Broker will be in charge to collect the metadata related to the stored data. The publish and subscribe paradigm allows each component, that needs specific data, to retrieve the updated information provided by another component. This mechanism guarantees data integration and the context data management is based on NGSIv2/NGSI-LD APIs [17].

TEMA solution deals with big data that will be collected, exchanged and analyzed. This huge amount of data entails different structures and formats to expose the information. The adoption of common data models will assure the data interoperability, also ensuring that the entities to be merged or aggregated are combined meaningfully.

5 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented an overall architecture for supporting first responders during and after a natural disaster. The main aims are inherited by the TEMA goals and are intended to be achieved by using cutting-edge technologies and paradigms, such as the computing continuum and the federated learning. A novel software architecture was, therefore, proposed to facilitate the process of decision-making at the edge of the network, while maintaining cloud computing as data storage and extremely intensive computation unit. Mobile and stationary devices are included in that architecture and each of them can be part of an independent local model training, which leads to the creation of a common global model. FIWARE, the cloud platform proposed by the European Commission, is used for facilitating a publishing/subscribe communication from and to the cloud. Tasks may be offloaded according to limited resources of battery-powered devices.

Our intention is validating the architecture both from a design and implementation point of view. We will draw interaction, use cases and class diagrams to make more robust the design. Therefore, we will implement such architecture involving the use of ROS as middleware for interfacing deep edge devices (e.g., drones), ground stations and the DE.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Yousuf Alhinai. 2020. Disaster Management Digitally Transformed: Exploring the Impact and Key Determinants from the UK National Disaster Management Experience. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 51 (09 2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2020.101851>
- [2] Daniel Balouek-Thomert, Eddy Caron, Laurent Lefevre, and Manish Parashar. 2022. Towards a Methodology for Building Dynamic Urgent Applications on Continuum Computing Platforms. *Proceedings of CIW-IUS 2022: Combined International Workshop on Interactive Urgent Supercomputing, Held in conjunction with SC 2022: The International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis* (2022), 25–30. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CIW-IUS56691.2022.00009>
- [3] Daniel Balouek-Thomert, Eduard Gibert Renart, Ali Reza Zamani, Anthony Simonet, and Manish Parashar. 2019. Towards a computing continuum: Enabling edge-to-cloud integration for data-driven workflows. *International Journal of High Performance Computing Applications* 33 (11 2019), 1159–1174. Issue 6. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094342019877383/FORMAT/EPUB>
- [4] Daniel Balouek-Thomert, Ivan Rodero, and Manish Parashar. 2020. Harnessing the Computing Continuum for Urgent Science. *ACM SIGMETRICS Performance*

- Evaluation Review* 48 (11 2020), 41–46. Issue 2. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3439602.3439618>
- [5] Daniel Balouek-Thomert, Pedro Silva, Kevin Fauvel, Alexandru Costan, Gabriel Antoniu, and Manish Parashar. 2021. MDSC: Modelling distributed stream processing across the edge-to-cloud continuum. *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series* (12 2021). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3492323.3495590>
- [6] Nitesh Bharosa, Jinkyu Lee, and Marijn Janssen. 2010. Challenges and Obstacles in Sharing and Coordinating Information During Multi-Agency Disaster Response. *Information Systems Frontiers* 12 (03 2010), 49–65. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-009-9174-z>
- [7] Shuiguang Deng, Hailiang Zhao, Weijia Fang, Jianwei Yin, Schahram Dustdar, and Albert Y. Zomaya. 2020. Edge Intelligence: The Confluence of Edge Computing and Artificial Intelligence. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* 7 (8 2020), 7457–7469. Issue 8. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2020.2984887>
- [8] Chiara Fonio and Adam Widera. 2020. *Trial Guidance Methodology Handbook*.
- [9] Institute for Economics Peace. 2020. Ecological Threat Register 2020: Understanding Ecological Threats. Resilience and Peace, Sydney.
- [10] L. Marasso G. Aiello, M. Alessi. 2016. City Enabler: a FIWARE based tool for crawling, collecting and rendering on a map valuable data at urban scale. *Second CINI Annual Workshop on ICT for Smart Cities and Communities I-Cities* (2016).
- [11] Dragi Kimovski, Roland Matha, Josef Hammer, Narges Mehran, Hermann Hellwagner, and Radu Prodan. 2021. Cloud, Fog, or Edge: Where to Compute? *IEEE Internet Computing* 25 (7 2021), 30–36. Issue 4. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MIC.2021.3050613>
- [12] H. Brendan McMahan, Eider Moore, Daniel Ramage, Seth Hampson, and Blaise Agüera y Arcas. 2016. Communication-Efficient Learning of Deep Networks from Decentralized Data. *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics, AISTATS 2017* (2 2016). <https://arxiv.org/abs/1602.05629v4>
- [13] MinIO. 2023. *MinIO Resources*. <https://resources.min.io/l/library>
- [14] Andrés Muñoz-Arcenales, Sonsoles López-Pernas, Javier Conde, Álvaro Alonso, Joaquín Salvachúa, and Juan José Hierro. 2021. Enabling Context-Aware Data Analytics in Smart Environments: An Open Source Reference Implementation. *Sensors (Basel, Switzerland)* 21 (2021). <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:240092693>
- [15] Daniel Rosendo, Alexandru Costan, Patrick Valduriez, and Gabriel Antoniu. 2022. Distributed intelligence on the Edge-to-Cloud Continuum: A systematic literature review. *J. Parallel and Distrib. Comput.* 166 (2022), 71–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpdc.2022.04.004>
- [16] Engineering Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A. 2023. *Ecosystem Platform Digital Enabler*. <https://www.eng.it/en/our-platforms-solutions/digital-enabler>
- [17] ETSI The standard people. 2023. *ETSI White Paper*. https://www.etsi.org/images/ñAles/ETSIWhitePapers/etsi_wp_42_NGSI_LD.pdf
- [18] Y. Supriya and Thippa Reddy Gadekallu. 2023. Particle Swarm-Based Federated Learning Approach for Early Detection of Forest Fires. *Sustainability* 2023, Vol. 15, Page 964 15 (1 2023), 964. Issue 2. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU15020964>
- [19] Rabia Tehseen, Muhammad Shoaib Farooq, and Adnan Abid. 2021. EPS: An earthquake prediction system using Federated Learning. *4th International Conference on Innovative Computing, ICIC 2021* (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIC53490.2021.9692919>
- [20] Rabia Tehseen, Muhammad Shoaib Farooq, and Adnan Abid. 2021. A Framework for the Prediction of Earthquake Using Federated Learning. *PeerJ Computer Science* 7 (5 2021), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.7717/PEERJ-CS.540/SUPP-2>
- [21] Silvia Torresan, Andrea Critto, Jonathan Rizzi, Alex Zabeo, Elisa Furlan, and Antonio Marcomini. 2016. DESYCO: A decision support system for the regional risk assessment of climate change impacts in coastal zones. *Ocean Coastal Management* 120 (2 2016), 49–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.OCECOAMAN.2015.11.003>
- [22] Wei Zhang and Xiao Chen. 2022. Model Driven Architecture In GIS-based DSS for flood management. *2022 3rd International Conference on Geology, Mapping and Remote Sensing, ICGMRS 2022* (2022), 918–921. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICGMRS55602.2022.9849280>